

SPECIFICATION OF "FRIEND" ASSOCIATIVE FIELD VERBAL ASSOCIATIONS

H.R.Zakirova

Andijan state university

associate professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8375251>

Annotation: This article is based on the principle of determining the associative field of the word "friend" from the linguistic point of view of the specifics of verbal associations on the example of the associative field "friend". The associative field of Uzbek words and their points of connection with the stimulus word were considered in the work. Several manifestations of the associative field are analyzed in connection with various factors: general and personal according to the character of the language owners; such as permanent (traditional) and temporary in terms of actuality. It was observed that the associations with the stimulus word appear grammatically in the same form, sometimes in different forms, and the properties of associations belonging to different levels in the same field were studied.

Keywords: associative field, Uzbek language, actuality, language owners, connection, linguistic consciousness, thinking, psyche, linguistics, pragmatolinguistics, sociolinguistics

In Uzbek linguistics, too, serious attention is paid to the study of language units in contact with external factors such as linguistic consciousness and thinking, psyche, gender, age characteristics, national-cultural views, professional-Cory of language owners who use it. This approach to the study of language paved the way for the development of associative linguistics, among other areas of anthropocentric linguistics, such as cognitive linguistics, pragmatolinguistics, sociolinguistics. In associative linguistics, a language, its units are studied in its pure form, in other words, in this direction the natural state of the language up to the colloquial application is analyzed. In this respect, the study of the associative field and its elements, the specificity of verbal associations, one of the main concepts of associative linguistics, is counted from the factors that determine the relevance of the problem.

The term "association" was introduced by the English philosopher John Locke. He wrote in his book "Опыт о человеке разумении" that association as a psychological phenomenon, "The process in which the emergence of one idea causes the appearance of another, connected in some way with the first"¹. John Locke was the first to use the term "thought Association".

One of the central concepts of associative linguistics is the question of associative relation. The associative attitude is the attitude of language units based on the human psychological imagination, reflecting the mechanism of "memorizing each other". On the basis of this relationship lies the concept of association.

Therefore, Association is understood as the relationship of a person with the activity of thinking, subjective experience and knowledge of certain objects and phenomena that exist in human thinking and are realizable in speech. The associative field, on the other hand, is a certain reality, structurally lexicographic in nature, reflected in the human mind, the verbal expression of the image of its companions, the imagination of it, the sum of the units of the

¹ Локк Дж. Сочинения в 3-х т./ под.ред. И.С.Нарского, 1985. -С 432

language that demonstrate knowledge in a mutually associatively connected semantic and grammatical relationship.

In associative linguistics, the associative field is basically formulated in 2 different ways:

- 1) method of associative experience performed on language holders;
- 2) method of marking the associative area of the finished text.

We used the first method when forming the associative field "friend". Such an experiment is carried out on a large number of language owners. In this, the owners of the language are asked to write the first word or word combination, a sentence, in the distributed questionnaire, which comes to their memory according to the impulse word, which is read in a certain period of time. An associative field is formed based on summing up all the results after the polls are collected.

We used the survey method when forming the associative field "friend". Considering that the composition of the associative field "friend" is different, the questionnaire was structured as follows:

ASSOCIATIVE EXPERIENCE SURVEY

No		Response reactions
1	Synonyms	comrade ...
2	Antonyms	enemy ...
3	bandmate	sirdash...
4	Coming in a portable sense	the book is our friend ...
5	Proverbs	build a good house with a friend
6	Aphorisms	
7	Examples from fiction	
8	Associative units	Partner, satellite ...
9	Possibility of making	friendship ...

This survey was conducted among students of the second stage (118 students) and professors (20 students) of Andijan state university. The results obtained were as follows:

Friend: friend(65), soul(52), dugona(60), oshna(72), comrade (84), ogayni (56), yor(18), partner (12), companion (8), confidant (20), brother (64), liver (16), venerable (20), comrade (16), peer (8), shoulder (8), mercenary (12), ulfat (12), hamdam-u PARTNER (2), friend-confidant (2), traitor (8), god (1), Habib (1), enemy(70), yov (50), opponent (62), competitor (14), agyor (16), Ghanim (7), traitor (10), stranger (12), Evil (6), Yogi (12), tyrant (20), tukhmatchi (20), counter (18), devil (2), Black Power (2), Evil (4), unclean (4), concubine (4), sister(2), secrecy (4), help (6), affection (8), consequence (10), friendliness (22), friendship (27), loyalty (28), Fidelity (26), childhood (56), mystery (10), sympathy (28), yupanch (18), trust (34), like-minded (40), partner (32), loving (38), close man (53), kindness (22), solidarity (42), togetherness (53), confidant (43), parent (10), brother (8), sister (10), classmate (21), comrade-in-arms (28), gruppadosh (30), parable (38), sister (1), coursework (24), mahalladosh (42), colleague (30), partadosh (24), fellow (29), schoolmate (34), there is such a "friend"Im, who keeps me awake for the night in search for a shot. Sendaqa prefers one friend, a thousand enemies. If you have such a friend, the enemy does not need (43). Even my friends are disappointed in the hostility of you. The friend looks like wine, the more'show good. There are two friends, not seeing each other (42). The book is my friend (50). My dog Olapar is my most

devoted companion. Horses are loyal friends (20). So if "friend" ing, the enemy na darkor. My head without friends, my soup without salt (76). Looking for an innocent friend, staying friendless (80). Do not believe in your friend, and in your straw tie(46). A lone horse does not get thirsty, nor does it get thirsty. The friend will speak in pity, the enemy will laugh (80). The friend does not take much of it. The friend is known in the cult (82). Build a good house with a friend, if you gar, neither woe nor ruin if the friend does not step, nor kashona(76). Your friend is little, even if he is a thousand, and the enemy is one. Of the ten fake friends, one true friend is good. Fish without water-a person cannot live without friends. The power of the Eagle is on the foot, that of man – in friendship. With a tree trunk, with a human friend(56). Barley-wheat will suit you for a day, live until your faithful friend dies. The enemy comes out of the friend. Keep the tree alive, friend of Adam(45). Die for your friend orphan. The friend will feed the friend, and the water will flow into the shade. Wing to a friend friend. A friend will follow, and an enemy will follow. The stone that the friend threw is headless. Even if the friend is far away, disappointment is close. I told a friend my word, the enemy knew my secret. It is easy to be an enemy to a friend, it is difficult to be a friend to an enemy. Take poison for your friend. Friends are not always friends (Lermontov). There is more joy than the diydor of friends, more grief than the firoki (Rudakiy). Approach the sage, run away from the fool, because he is dangerous from the wise dushmsn (J.Rumi). In order to truly associate, a person needs to trust each other (L.Tolstoy). If you make a new friend, do not turn away from the old one (Qobus). For a friend, it is even more honorable to give life to a friend every day in some unexpected circumstances than to abandon the Pinkhouse (Stendal). Loneliness is better than evil comrade (Qobus). It is useful to see some person in the enemy row rather than in the friend Row (F. Dostoyevsky). A person who is friends with everyone is not friends with anyone (Arastu). Since today, my friend has been two: one – a portfolio, the other – binoculars (Genghis Aitmatov. White ship). In those times when my joy did not fit into me, for some reason I became a frequent memory of my friend Orif (X.Tokaboyev. Riding a yellow giant). I said goodbye to my cherished cap a second time that day. - Goodbye, my cap! - I said, taking tears in my eyes, - we will see again. "Goodbye, my cheerful friend," my cap also cried, " of course, we will see (X.Tokaboyev. Riding a yellow giant). I thought I was standing on top of my friend. How can I explain to him that his opinion is xató (X.Tokaboyev. Riding a yellow giant). On a difficult day, a sailing man, a loving man, for a friend, towards a friend, trust in a friend, can tell him what you can't tell anyone, in any case, be sympathetic, encouraging, close confidant, devoted to a friend, merciful friend, ties or equates equals, to be together in any situation, friendship is great strength, cunning to a friend, prudence, friendship is great strength, true friend, loyalty to a friend, masjahatlaşi, a girl next door who plays a game together in youth, solidarity, morality, consequence, tentacles in youth, lesson escapes, who read to others, pure competition, a good beginner, support, solidarity, enthusiasm, compassion, gentle volunteering. A comrade in soup, a heel to the head, such friends will share food. Friendship(3), friendless(5), friendship(20), cookery(4), ulfati young man, comrade, Friendly(14), comrade(), agony, Ulfat (7), comrade(2), Brotherhood, for Friend(3), Friend(3), hospitable(2), Comrade(2), sailman, friendship(2), sailman, ulfateri, friendship, juraboshi, Brotherhood, dostfurush, dardakash, like friends.

As can be seen from the above, together with semantically connected units to the associative field, restored units in memory are also united, not semantically connected, in connection with the psyche, worldview, interests, knowledge of the universe of language owners. Such units are pre-nutty Language units-lexical units, phrases, matals, Proverbs,

Proverbs, certain vocabulary and sentences that are used in the speech of language owners as a stable unit, as well as speech syntactic units that are formed in the speech process.

We analyzed this associative field as follows:

I. Lexical semantic mark of the friend lexeme. The lexical meaning of the friend lexeme. The "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language" gives the following meanings of the friendly lexeme: 1. Bound by a relationship of cow, harmony, harmony, heart, dili close. 2. Supporter, patron. 3. Application form. 4. In religious mysticism: God.

These meanings have been found to be real in the following associations of the friendly lexeme:

1. Bound by a relationship of cow, harmony, harmony, heart, dili close: dear friend, true friend. They were friends from a young age. From work, friend ortar. Do not say a secret that your friend has a friend. Friendly nations. Close, familiar, oshno. John is a sincere, selfless friend who does not spare his friend John. A business friend is an earned friend who works together. Work friend - John friend. The mole friend picked up and earned a friend, a superficial friend who was in the hope of something. Even though John Does Away With John, mol does not go away with the dozing mill. Piri doesn't have friends either, it's about a bad guy who won't be friends with anyone. The ball from a friend is said when his friend, a loved one, makes some intimacy.

2. Supporter, patron. One day, Emerald looked at meh and said, " My Friend, our government is sucking women's friends, they are also willing, they say that they live like a man with their own husband..." S.Zunununova. Bonfire.

3. Application form. Mature, friend! - So why is the guilt raw? - E, dear friend, I was left with little difficulty. N.Safarov, School of life.

4. In religious mysticism: God. From near all times, the sound of God is heard: "Hey Friend, shaydullo, banomi ollo, alms rejected balo, God of the noble Messenger". A.Kahhor. Patient. Draw a friend: 1) beg God as " Friend"; 2) roar, roar.

II. Semantic components of a friend's lexeme: the chief meaning of a friend's lexeme is disappointment, with close semantic components of dili. These SEMAS come to the surface in their following associations: trust, loyalty, sympathy, suyansa, help in a difficult situation, support, understand the heart, etc.

Portable meanings of a friend's lexeme: there is such a "friend", the one who shoots me spends the night awake in search of a bullet. Sendaqa prefers one friend, a thousand enemies. If you have such a friend, the enemy does not need (43). Even my friends are disappointed that I have an enemy like you. The friend looks like wine, the more the better. There are two friends, not seeing each other (42). The book is my friend (50). My dog Olapar is my most devoted companion. Horses are loyal friends (20). So if "friend" ing, the enemy na darkor.

Paradigmatic series of friend lexemes. In paradigmatic lines of the friend's lexeme, words related to the noun (oshna, ogayni, comrade, trust, consequence, loyalty and hakazo), adjective (friendly, faithful, friendly), number (many, few, impudent), verb (to befriend, to be Ulfat, to be faithful), multiple verbal conjugations (for a friend, with a friend, to be oshna), few phrases (life without friends), syntaxemes in sentence structure (friend caught, friend

The synonymic attitude was observed in the following associations: friend, Jura, dugona, oshna, comrade, ogayni, yor, partner, companion, confidant, brother, liver, venerable, comrade,

peer, sailman, mercenary, ulfat, hamdam-he is a partner, friend-confidant, concubine, God, habib.

The antonymic attitude was observed by the following associations: enemy, yov, opponent, competitive, agyor, Ghanim, traitor, alien, evil, fat, tyrant, tactician, counter, devil, Black Power, evil, unclean, hamtovak.

Parthonimic attitude the following pair of assotsuations were observed: friend-enemy, friend-companion, friend-loyalty, friend-ulfatsiya.

The lines of shame are: sister, secrecy, help, affection, consequence, friendliness, friendship, loyalty, fidelity, childhood, mystery, sympathy, yupanch, trust, like-minded, partner, kind, close person, Kindness, Harmony, togetherness, confidant, parent, brother, sister, classmate, gunman, gruppadosh, parlahat, sister, coursework, mahalladosh, colleague, partadosh, Safad, schoolmate.

III. Lexical-grammatical mark of the friend lexeme. On the basis of associative experience, associations of a friend's lexeme in the following morphological forms were noted: from a friend, friend, friend, friend, chef. A characteristic aspect characteristic of the friendly lexeme verbal associations is that many associative vocabulary combinations were observed in it, Associations in the sentence structure also occur.

The word friend base directly enters into a syntagmatic relationship with the following associations: loyalty to a friend, in favor of a friend, drinking with oshnas, drinking with a comrade, making a fortune-telling.

In the associative field of the friend lexeme, the following colloquial syntagmatic links were observed: soul mate, friend lessons, to do for a friend, to accompany a friend, friend bilam to be together.

Shakily syntactic relation representations in the associative field:

- 1) equal attitude: friend-enemy, friend-companion;*
- 2) subordinate attitude manifestations: a) management: loyalty to a friend, destruction of a friend, expectation from a Friend; b) adaptation: a friend's room, a friend's house; v) contiguous: first friend, a night of friends, a dear friend.*

Meaningful syntagmatic relation views:

- 1) predicative attitude: seeing a friend, waiting for a friend;*
- 2) attributive attitude: dear friend, urban friend;*
- 3) relational attitude: avoiding ulfatness, hoping for a friend;*
- 4) objective attitude: bully from a friend.*

IV. Derivational property of the friend lexeme. On the basis of associative experience, the following lexical associations were identified, made on the basis of a friend's lexeme: befriend, friendless, friendship, cookery, ulfati young man, comrade, friendliness, companionship, generosity, companionship, for a friend, with a friend, hospitable, empathetic, helmsman, companionship, barnyard, companionship, courtship, Brotherhood, companionship, sorrows, friends.

V. Methodological mark of the friend lexeme. In the associations of the lexeme of a friend, the following associations are identified, which are stylistically characteristic: a) artistic style - a bond of friendship; B) colloquial style - culinary, againI; C) scientific style - social communication; g) publicistic style - friendly meeting, friendship ties.

VI. Pragmatic sign of the friend lexeme. Connotation feature. Connotative meaning has been generated through the metaphorical applications of a loving person, facilitator, youth temtakliklar, facilitator, challenger, taking place from the associative field of the friend lexeme.

Representation of the evaluation relation. The verbal associations of the friendly lexeme also reflected the negative and positive attitudes of language owners towards the vagaries that occurred in connection with their youth life. The friend was observed to be reflected in the following associations as an expression of multifaceted events in a person's life: in associations such as kindness, intimacy, trust, confidentiality, the positive attitude of language owners is vividly reflected.

The following associations have come to light in relation to school life in a person: Treason, Treason, errors in youth, the stay of congil.

VII. Gender marker of the friend lexeme. The following associations of the friend lexeme differ according to the gender sign: friend, dugona, jamalak-haired comrade, oshnam, ulfat.

VIII. National-cultural mark of the friend lexeme. In the following associations of the friend lexeme, the sign of nationality comes to the surface: sympathize in life, eat poison for your friend.

IX. A sign of sociability of a friend's lexeme. The sign of sociability of associations associated with a friend's lexeme is clearly visible in the following pairs: friend-enemy, colleague-friend at work, classmate-friend, coursework-friend.

X. Associative space of the friend lexeme. The basis of the associative field of the friendly lexeme is a wide range of applications, to which proverbs, aphorisms, examples in fiction and associative units are formed. Associative units: sailing on a hard day, a loving person, for a friend, towards a friend, trust in a friend, you can tell him what you can't tell anyone, in any case, a sympathetic, encouraging, close confidant, faithful to a friend, a merciful friend, ties or equates equals, being together in any situation, friendship is a great power, cunning to a friend, an expert, friendship is a great power, true friend, loyalty to a friend, glazing, masjahat with a friend, a girl next door who plays games together in youth, solidarity, morality, consequence, tentacles in youth, lesson evils, who read books to others, pure competition, a beginner in a good way, support, solidarity, enthusiasm, compassion, gentle volunteering. A comrade in soup, a heel to the head, such friends will share food. Examples from fiction: from today my friend became two: one – a portfolio, the other-binoculars (Genghis Aitmatov. White ship). In those times when my joy did not fit into me, for some reason I became a frequent memory of my friend Orif (X.Tokaboyev. Riding a yellow giant). I said goodbye to my cherished cap a second time that day. - Goodbye, my cap! - I said, taking tears in my eyes, - we will see again. "Goodbye, my cheerful friend," my cap also cried, " of course, we will see (X.Tokaboyev. Riding a yellow giant). I thought I was standing on top of my friend. How can I explain to him that his opinion is xató (X.Tokaboyev. Riding a yellow giant). Aphorisms: friends are not always friends (Lermontov). There is more joy than the diydor of friends, more grief than the firoki (Rudakiy). Approach the sage, run away from the fool, because he is dangerous from the wise dushmsn (J.Rumi). In order to truly associate, a person needs to trust each other (L.Tolstoy).If you make a new friend, do not turn away from the old one (Qobus). For a friend, it is even more honorable to give life to a friend every day in some unexpected circumstances than to abandon the Pinkhouse (Stendal). Loneliness is better than evil comrade (Qobus). It is useful to see some person in the enemy row rather than in the friend Row (F. Dostoyevcky). A person who is friends with everyone is not friends with anyone (Arastu). Proverbs: my head without friends, my soup without salt. Looking for an innocent friend, they will be friendless. Do not believe in your friend, in your straw stopper. A lone horse does not get thirsty, nor does it get thirsty. The friend will speak in pity, the enemy will laugh. The friend does not take much of it. The friend is known in the cult. Build a good

house with a friend, if you gar, neither vayrona nor kashona, if the friend does not step, the ruin. Your friend is little, even if he is a thousand, and the enemy is one. Of the ten fake friends, one true friend is good. Fish without water-a person cannot live without friends. The power of the Eagle is on the foot, that of man – in friendship. With a tree trunk, with a human friend. Barley-wheat will suit you for a day, live until your faithful friend dies. The enemy comes out of the friend. The tree is kept alive, and the man is his friend . Die for your friend orphan. The friend will feed the friend, and the water will flow into the shade. Wing to a friend friend. A friend will follow, and an enemy will follow. The stone that the friend threw is headless. Even if the friend is far away, disappointment is close. I told a friend my word, the enemy knew my secret. It is easy to be an enemy to a friend, it is difficult to be a friend to an enemy. Take poison for your friend.

XI. Frequency of application of associatives. Statistical analysis of friend lexeme Associations shows that in all of the testers, the friend lexeme evokes the imagination as a person close to heart, dili, connected by a relationship of cowishness, harmony, harmony. For this reason, students were observed a classmate friend, dugona, meeting place, associations of interesting meetings. Aphorisms are also cited in adult language owners as well as evoking extralinguistic associations related to the early age of the friendly lexeme.

In the case of the frequency of application of the friendly associative field, the following conclusion can be made:

№	Friend associative space	quantity	%
1	Basic associative concepts	2214	77 %
2	Proverbs	556	19 %
3	Aphorisms	9	0,60 %
4	Examples from fiction	4	0,40 %
5	Possibility of making	75	3 %
	Total:	2858	100 %

Hence, in the example of the “friend” associative field, the verbal associations specification is related to private ones such as personality psyche, psychic state, social status. Yu.N.Karaulov had shown the following about the importance of studying the associative Field: 1) any combination of words formed by the combination of the impulse word and the response reaction can be seen as a colloquial model, which means that the associative field acts as a source in the construction of vocabulary training tasks, exercises; 2) two-word models are the building material; 3) rich information in the set of units occupied by the associative field multi-valued motivation makes it possible to demonstrate the realization of all meanings inherent in the word, to determine its synonymous, antonymic, paronymic, homonymic and other relationships; 4) the associative verbal network includes not only lexical and grammatical, but also cognitive and pragmatic information, associative field structure, in which the separation of².

² Караулов Ю.Н. Русский ассоциативный словарь как новый лингвистический источник и инструмент анализа языковой способности // Русский ассоциативный словарь. Книга 1. (Ю.Н. Караулов, Ю.А. Сорокин, Е.Ф. Тарасов, Н.В. Уфимцева, Г.А. Черкасова. – М.: Помовский и партнеры, 1994 б.) – С. 191-218.

References:

1. Локк Дж. Сочинения в 3-х т./ под.ред. И.С.Нарского, 1985. -С 432
2. Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати: 80 мингдан ортиқ сўз ва сўз бирикмаси. Ж. П. Е-М. (Т.Мирзаев ва бошқ.) – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси, 2006. - Б.532.
3. Караулов Ю.Н. Русский ассоциативный словарь как новый лингвистический источник и инструмент анализа языковой способности // Русский ассоциативный словарь. Книга 1. (Ю.Н. Караулов, Ю.А. Сорокин, Е.Ф. Тарасов, Н.В. Уфимцева, Г.А. Черкасова. – М.: Помовский и партнеры, 1994 б.) – С. 191-218.

